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THE IMPORTANCE OF QUALIFIED MEDICAL CARE IN REDUCING MATERNAL AND CHILD MORTALITY

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Abstract: *This article analyzes the importance of qualified medical care in reducing maternal and child mortality. The effectiveness of quality medical monitoring during pregnancy, the participation of qualified specialists in the delivery process, and postpartum care is highlighted. The role of modern diagnostic methods, preventive measures, and primary health care in maintaining maternal and child health is also highlighted. The article describes the main causes of maternal and child mortality and recommendations for their reduction.*

Keywords: *maternal and child mortality, qualified medical care, reproductive health, pregnancy, childbirth, neonatal period, prevention, quality of medical services, maternal health, child health, perinatal care, diagnostics, obstetrics, pediatrics, healthcare system.*

Today, protecting the health of mothers and children is one of the most important areas of the global health system. Maternal and child mortality is one of the main indicators determining the level of socio-economic development of society, and this problem remains relevant in many countries. In particular, the lack of adequate organization of qualified medical care during pregnancy, childbirth and the postpartum period leads to the emergence of various complications. Therefore, improving the system of providing qualified medical care is of great importance in reducing maternal and child mortality.

Maternal and child mortality is caused by a variety of factors. These include pregnancy complications, malnutrition, infectious diseases, malnutrition, poor quality of medical services, and a shortage of qualified specialists. The problem is exacerbated by the underdevelopment of medical services, especially in rural areas.

Qualified medical care allows pregnant women to undergo regular medical examinations, conduct laboratory and instrumental examinations, and identify risk factors early. During pregnancy, constant monitoring of a woman's blood pressure, hemoglobin levels, and fetal development helps prevent complications. In particular, timely detection of preeclampsia, eclampsia, bleeding, and infections is an important factor in saving the mother's life.

The participation of qualified obstetricians-gynecologists and nurses in the birth process is very important. The availability of modern medical technologies and sterile conditions reduces the risks of childbirth. Also, the availability of emergency medical care helps to save the lives of the mother and child in difficult situations.

Premature birth, respiratory failure, infections, and birth defects are among the leading causes of infant mortality. Providing quality medical care to infants in the neonatal period, properly organizing breastfeeding, and timely vaccinations can significantly reduce infant mortality.

Preventive measures are also important. Increasing the population's medical literacy, promoting a healthy lifestyle, and conducting explanatory work on reproductive health will improve the health of mothers and children. Increasing the funds allocated by the state to the health system will also allow improving the quality of medical services.

Today, large-scale reforms are being implemented in Uzbekistan to protect the health of mothers and children. As a result of the development of perinatal centers, the introduction of modern diagnostic equipment, and the improvement of the system for training qualified personnel, maternal and child mortality rates are decreasing.

In conclusion, qualified medical care is one of the most important factors in reducing maternal and child mortality. Regular monitoring of pregnancy, delivery with the participation of qualified specialists, improving the quality of neonatal care, and strengthening preventive measures can maintain the health of mothers and children. Further development of the health care system and increasing the medical culture of the population will contribute to the healthy growth of the future generation.

The main causes of maternal death include severe bleeding, arterial hypertension, sepsis, complications of childbirth and unsafe abortions. These conditions are often aggravated by the lack of timely medical care or the lack of qualified specialists. In particular, the lack of regular medical supervision during pregnancy leads to late detection of pathological changes in the woman's body.

The main causes of infant mortality are premature birth, low birth weight, respiratory failure, infectious diseases, and poor care. Since infants have a weak immune system, they are susceptible to various diseases. Therefore, qualified medical supervision in the neonatal period is of particular importance.

The development of modern medical technologies creates a great opportunity to reduce maternal and child mortality. Ultrasound examination, laboratory diagnostics, prenatal screening and resuscitation methods make it possible to detect dangerous conditions early. Regular monitoring of pregnant women, especially those in high-risk groups, helps to prevent complications.

The establishment of modern perinatal centers also allows for the safe delivery of complex births. Neonatal intensive care units provide special care to newborns, increasing their survival rate.

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